

German market for smartphones grows faster than expected. Total revenues for 2015 increase by 7 per cent to 9,1 billion Euro (bitkom.org, 10.08.2015)

Consuming Information and Communication Technologies

How can information and communication technology be consumed more sustainably?

Overview

We borrow the earth from our children, therefore striving for sustainable development asks for a critical inquiry of the interdependencies between human consumption of information and communication technologies (ICTs) and nature. ICTs constitute one of the sources of climate degradation and bring with it ecological, economic and social costs. We intend to start a dialogue and invite the *digital society* to join the endeavor of transforming consumption.

Consuming Technologies

At eColnnovateIT we follow an interdisciplinary approach to seeking knowledge about consumers, combining the expertise of anthropology, sociology and psychology. This allows us to inquire the choices of individual consumers as well as the social structuration of consumer practices located in collectively shared imaginaries. In particular we are interested in understanding the cultural norms that guide the lived experience within communities of consumption.

New Directions

Through understanding the lived experience of subcultures, we intend to contextualise consumption and uncover barriers to more sustainable lifestyles. In our model of open innovation the contradictions we encounter provide stimuli for change. Through enacting societal dialogue alternative forms of ICT consumption are explored, which may form the base of transforming the dominant mode of consumption.

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Further Research Topics

- Organizations and their Consumers
- Qualitative Research Methods
- Management of Family Firms
- Competence-based Strategic Management

Teaching Activity

- Business Anthropology
- Entrepreneurship Education
- Macro-marketing

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